

BUCKLING OF LAMINATED CIRCULAR CYLINDRICAL SHELLS
WITH DIFFERENT MODULI IN TENSION AND COMPRESSION*

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ABSTRACT

An exact buckling criterion, within the framework of classical buckling theory, is derived for laminated circular cylindrical shells made of materials that have different orthotropic moduli in tension and compression. Such behavior is typical of many current composite materials. The buckling criterion is valid for arbitrary combinations of axial and circumferential loading, including axial compression and internal pressure as well as axial tension and lateral pressure. The material model (stress-strain relationship) is based on a bilinear stress-strain curve with a discontinuity in slope (modulus) at the origin. Numerical results are used to illustrate application of the buckling criterion. In particular, results are given for single-layered isotropic and orthotropic shells with noticeable differences in tensile and compressive moduli. Moreover, results are shown for shells laminated of advanced composite materials.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are receiving dramatically increasing attention for many aerospace structural applications because up to 40% in weight can be saved over alternative metal materials [1]. Laminated composite plates and shells are basic aerospace structural elements whose use in the latest aircraft and missile structures depends

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on precise knowledge of their behavior. Thus, accurate design analysis tools are essential for these uses of composite materials.

One significant characteristic of composite materials is their different behavior under tensile and compressive loads. Both the elastic moduli (stiffnesses) and the strengths in principal material property directions are different for tensile loading than for compressive loading. The characteristic stiffness behavior (strength behavior will not be treated) is shown schematically as the bilinear stress-strain curve of Figure 1. This phenomenon is but one of several differences that make composite materials harder to analyze (and hence design) than more common materials such as aluminum.

Actual stress-strain behavior probably exhibits a nonlinear transition region between the tension and compression linear portions of the stress-strain curve. (The measurement of strains near zero stress is difficult to perform accurately.) Replacement of actual behavior by a bilinear model in Figure 1 is offered as a simplification of obviously nonlinear behavior. For most materials, the mechanical property data are insufficient to justify use of a more complex material model. However, one possible disadvantage of the bilinear stress-strain curve approximation is that a discontinuity in slope (modulus) occurs at the origin of the stress-strain curve.

Both fiber-reinforced and granular composite materials have different moduli in tension and compression as displayed in Table 1. Unidirectional glass fibers in an epoxy matrix have compressive moduli 20% lower than the tensile moduli [2]. For some unidirectional boron/epoxy fiber-reinforced laminae, the compressive moduli are about

15-20% larger than the tensile moduli [3]. In contrast, some unidirectional graphite/epoxy fiber-reinforced laminae have tensile moduli up to 40% greater than the compressive moduli [3]. Other fiber-reinforced composites such as carbon/carbon have tensile moduli from two to five times the compressive moduli [4]. Thus, no clear pattern of larger tensile than compressive moduli or vice versa exists for fiber-reinforced composite materials. For granular composite materials, the tensile versus compressive moduli situation is no clearer. ZTA graphite has tensile moduli as much as 20% lower than the compressive moduli [6].

Fig. 1 Stress-Strain Curve for a Material with Different Moduli in Tension and Compression

Many other composite materials have different tensile and compressive moduli. Which modulus is higher may depend on the fiber or granule stiffness relative to the matrix stiffness. A general physical explanation of different behavior in tension and compression is not yet available. Investigation of the micromechanical behavioral aspects of composite materials may lead to a rational explanation of this phenomenon. Even without such an explanation, the apparent be-

Table 1 Tensile and Compressive Moduli Relationships

MATERIAL	FIBEROUS OR GRANULAR	REPRESENTATIVE MODULI RELATIONSHIP
GLASS/EPOXY	FIBEROUS	$E_t = 1.25E_c$
BORON/EPOXY	FIBEROUS	$E_c = 1.2E_t$
GRAPHITE/EPOXY	FIBEROUS	$E_t = 1.4E_c$
CARBON/CARBON	FIBEROUS	$E_t = 2-5E_t$
ZTA GRAPHITE	GRANULAR	$E_c = 1.2E_t$
ATJ-S GRAPHITE	GRANULAR	$E_t = 1.2E_c$

havior can be used in analyzing the stress-strain behavior of materials. That is, even without knowing why the materials behave as they do, we can model their apparent behavior.

Given that the uniaxial stress-strain behavior is approximated by a bilinear representation, the definition remains of the multi-axial stress-strain relations required in structural analysis. Over the past ten years, Ambartsumyan and his co-workers [7-10], in the process of obtaining stresses in shells and bodies of revolution, defined stress-strain relations referred to as the Ambartsumyan material model. Tabaddor [11] elaborated on the Ambartsumyan material model. Jones [12] applied the model to buckling under biaxial loading of circular cylindrical shells made of an isotropic material.

In application of the Ambartsumyan material model to orthotropic materials, however, certain deficiencies, such as a nonsymmetric compliance matrix in the stress-strain relations [13], are apparent. Jones [14] applied modified bilinear stress-strain relations to buckling of shells with multiple layers of orthotropic materials having different moduli in tension and compression. His modifications consist of weighting the tension and compression compliances according to the proportions of the principal stresses in order to obtain a symmetric compliance matrix. Isabekian and Khachatryan [15] made the Ambartsumyan material model have a symmetric compliance matrix by enforcing certain relations between the material properties. Their relations are used in this paper and contrasted with Jones' results.

The objective of this paper is to derive an analysis for and present numerical results for buckling of circular cylindrical shells with multiple orthotropic layers that have different moduli in tension than in compression. A cross-ply laminated circular cylindrical shell is shown in Figure 2 along with the loading (combinations of axial compression P and lateral pressure p). The term cross-ply is used to designate laminates of unidirectionally reinforced composite materials where the layers have fibers at either 0° or 90° to the laminate (shell) coordinates, e.g., x and y in Figure 2. Orthotropic woven or granular materials can also be treated if their principal material directions are aligned with the shell coordinates.

A new material model (stress-strain relationship) is developed as the basis for determining the variations in stresses during buckling. This paper is an extension of analyses of circular cylindrical shells with (1) eccentric stiffeners and multiple orthotropic layers

Fig. 2 Laminated Shell Geometry and Loading

[16], (2) different isotropic moduli in tension and compression using the Ambartsumyan material model [12], and (3) different orthotropic moduli in tension and compression [14]. The principal axes of orthotropy of the layers coincide with the shell coordinate directions. Each layer of the thin multilayered shell is perfectly bonded (i.e., a non-shear-deformable bond) to adjacent layers. Accordingly, the Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis is invoked as in conventional thin shell theory. Classical buckling theory, by which is implied a membrane prebuckled shape, is used for S2 simply supported edge boundary conditions ($\delta N_x = \delta v = \delta w = \delta M_x = 0$) [17]. Coupling between bending and extension is not accounted for in the membrane prebuckling state but is treated during buckling. Under biaxial loading, the stress state in the layers is statically indeterminate because the material properties depend on the stresses. Procedures are developed for treating the indeterminacy. Next, a criterion is applied to determine the buckling load under arbitrary combinations of axial and lateral pressure including axial tension and external pressure as well as axial compression and internal pressure.

Application of the buckling criterion is illustrated with numerical results for single-layered and laminated shells. For single-layered shells, a representative isotropic material is studied. In addition, buckling loads are obtained for several common orthotropic composite materials. For laminated shells, results are found for a representative composite material as well as for a boron/epoxy shell.

2. DERIVATION OF BUCKLING CRITERION

The various moduli in the stress-strain relations for materials with different orthotropic moduli in tension and compression are chosen in the present material model according to the signs of the stresses in the indeterminate membrane prebuckling stress state. Thus, the membrane stress state must be found by searching for the combination of stress signs that is consistent with material properties in each layer which in turn lead to the same stress signs from the equilibrium equations. The variations in the biaxial stresses during buckling are then obtained in terms of the variations in strains in each layer of a multilayered circular cylindrical shell during buckling. Subsequently, the variations in biaxial stresses

are integrated over the shell layers in order to obtain expressions for the variations in forces and moments during buckling. Finally, the variations in forces and moments are substituted in Donnell-type buckling differential equations which are solved for a set of simply supported edge boundary conditions. The result is a closed-form buckling criterion in terms of the geometry and material properties of a laminated shell. The criterion is applicable for arbitrary combinations of axial and lateral pressure.

2.1 STRESS-STRAIN RELATIONS

For the orthotropic k^{th} layer of a multilayered shell subjected to principal stresses, σ_x^k and σ_y^k , in the shell coordinate directions and having principal axes of orthotropy aligned with the shell coordinate directions, the stress-strain relations are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \epsilon_x^k &= S_{11}^k \sigma_x^k + S_{12}^k \sigma_y^k \\ \epsilon_y^k &= S_{12}^k \sigma_x^k + S_{22}^k \sigma_y^k \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

The compliances, S_{ij}^k , are related to engineering constants for materials with the same moduli in tension and compression by

$$S_{11}^k = 1/E_x^k \quad S_{12}^k = -\nu_{xy}^k/E_x^k \quad S_{22}^k = 1/E_y^k \quad (2)$$

(for unidirectionally reinforced composites with fibers in the x -direction, $E_x = E_1$, $E_y = E_2$, and $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{12}$). The basic problem is to determine the compliances for materials with different moduli in tension and compression. Part of such a procedure is identification of new engineering constants which must be measured for such materials. These constants are more than just, for example, E_x^k in tension (E_{xt}^k) and E_x^k in compression (E_{xc}^k). Specifically, the new constants are related to shear behavior and will be determined in the section on relations between variations in stresses and variations in strains necessary for a buckling analysis. In the meantime, we will identify those moduli in tension and compression necessary to determine the membrane prebuckling state.

The compliances, S_{ij}^k , are determined in Ambartsumyan-related multimodulus material models according to the sign of the corresponding (principal) stresses:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{if } \sigma_x^k > 0, & \quad S_{11}^k = S_{11t}^k \\ \text{if } \sigma_x^k < 0, & \quad S_{11}^k = S_{11c}^k \\ \text{if } \sigma_y^k > 0, & \quad S_{22}^k = S_{22t}^k \\ \text{if } \sigma_y^k < 0, & \quad S_{22}^k = S_{22c}^k \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

The cross-compliance S_{12}^k has not been specified. Ambartsumyan [13] proposed that a separate S_{12t}^k and S_{12c}^k be determined for multimodulus materials. However, the strain-stress relations, Eq. (1), would then be unsymmetric (a potential function could not exist; thus, the usual solution procedures of elasticity theory could not be used). Jones [14] suggested a procedure for weighting the tensile and compressive cross-compliances according to the relative proportions of tensile and compressive stresses to obtain a single cross-compliance. Then, the usual procedures of elasticity can be used. However, Jones' weighted compliance model is arbitrary, i.e., not derivable from basic physical principles although it is an appropriate engineering approximation to this complex material modeling problem.

Isabekian and Khachatryan [15] obtain a material model that is more rational than Ambartsumyan's unsymmetric compliance model (and Jones' weighted compliance model which was developed after, but without knowledge of, Ref. 15). Cross-compliance symmetry is enforced by requiring the tensile and compressive cross-compliances to be equal. For stress states in which the principal stresses are not in principal material directions, all cross-compliances must be equal. As a consequence, the following restrictions on the compliances exist:

$$S_{11t}^k - S_{11c}^k = S_{22t}^k - S_{22c}^k \quad S_{12t}^k = S_{12c}^k \quad (4)$$

or, in terms of engineering constants,

$$\frac{1}{E_{xt}^k} - \frac{1}{E_{xc}^k} = \frac{1}{E_{yt}^k} - \frac{1}{E_{yc}^k} \quad \frac{\nu_{xyt}^k}{E_{xt}^k} = \frac{\nu_{xyc}^k}{E_{xc}^k} \quad (5)$$

Because of the compliance restrictions, only four independent material properties are required for specification of all possible stress states in Eq. (1). The other material properties are calculated by use of Eq. (5). However, these compliance restrictions may not be satisfied by all engineering materials.

2.2 DETERMINATION OF MEMBRANE PREBUCKLING STATE

In the preceding section, the compliances in the stress-strain relations are given for a single layer of a multilayered shell in terms of the layer stresses. However, the layer stresses cannot be determined from the shell geometry and loading alone; material properties must be known for each layer as well. Thus, in the membrane prebuckling state, both the layer stresses and material properties are indeterminate in a shell with multiple orthotropic layers that have different moduli in tension and compression. To resolve the prebuckling indeterminacy, iteration is required between a chosen set of stress signs and a set of stress signs calculated from material properties corresponding to the chosen set of stress signs until the two sets of stress signs agree.

The steps necessary to determine the membrane prebuckling state are depicted schematically in Figure 3. The first step is to make an arbitrary initial choice of the layer stress signs in order to start the procedure. For convenience, the initial choice is all negative signs to denote compressive stresses. The second step is to determine the compliances S_{11}^k and S_{22}^k for each layer from Eq. (3) according to the chosen stress signs. The third step is to calculate the relative membrane strains (relative because only the proportions of axial and compressive loading are required, not the magnitudes) from the given loading and the chosen material properties. The relative membrane strains are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{\epsilon}_x &= (k_1 A_{22} - k_2 A_{12}) / (A_{11} A_{22} - A_{12}^2) \\ \bar{\epsilon}_y &= (k_2 A_{11} - k_1 A_{12}) / (A_{11} A_{22} - A_{12}^2) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

which are obtained by inversion of the force-strain relations. In addition, the loading is redefined as $\bar{N}_x = k_1 \lambda$ and $\bar{N}_y = k_2 \lambda$ where λ is a measure of the magnitude of the loading and is used to normalize the actual strains to obtain the relative strains. In Eq. (6), the A_{ij} are the usual extensional stiffnesses of a laminate [18]. The fourth step is to calculate the relative layer stresses from

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_x^k &= Q_{11}^k \bar{\epsilon}_x^k + Q_{12}^k \bar{\epsilon}_y^k \\ \bar{\sigma}_y^k &= Q_{12}^k \bar{\epsilon}_x^k + Q_{22}^k \bar{\epsilon}_y^k \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

The reduced stiffnesses Q_{ij}^k are defined in terms of the compliances S_{ij}^k in the usual manner [18]. The fifth step is to compare the calculated stress signs with the chosen stress signs. If the two sets of signs agree, then a consistent membrane prebuckling state has been determined. Otherwise, another set of stress signs must be chosen and steps two through five repeated. Some of the possible ways of choosing the next set of stress signs are discussed by Jones [14].

Fig. 3 Logic for Determination of Membrane Prebuckling State

2.3 VARIATIONS OF STRESSES AND STRAINS DURING BUCKLING

During buckling, the stresses vary from their prebuckling values in the manner shown schematically in Figure 4 where E_t and E_c denote the tension and compression values of any orthotropic modulus. There, the variations of stresses occur in accordance with the sign of the pertinent stress with the corresponding modulus:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \delta\sigma_x^k &= Q_{11}^k \delta\epsilon_x^k + Q_{12}^k \delta\epsilon_y^k \\ \delta\sigma_y^k &= Q_{12}^k \delta\epsilon_x^k + Q_{22}^k \delta\epsilon_y^k \\ \delta\tau_{xy}^k &= Q_{66}^k \delta\gamma_{xy}^k \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 4 Variations of Stresses for a Material with Different Moduli in Tension and Compression

That is, buckling takes place under increasing stress (in the manner described by Shanley [19] with the moduli of the prebuckling equilibrium stresses. However, the variation of the stresses in Eq. (7) has been supplemented by a relation between the variations in shear stress and shear strain in Eq. (8). This relation is essential because the variation in shear stress during buckling is not zero even though the shear stress itself is zero for orthotropic layers in a laminated shell under axial pressure and lateral pressure.

The definition of Q_{66}^k in the relation between the variations in shear stress and strain is nontrivial. To determine Q_{66}^k , we first add variations of stresses during buckling, $\delta\sigma_x^k$, $\delta\sigma_y^k$, and $\delta\tau_{xy}^k$, to the prebuckling principal stresses, σ_x and σ_y for each layer. Thus, we define a new principal stress state at an (infinitesimally small) angle α from the x-direction as in Figure 5. Then, the new principal stress state is used to define material properties in the new principal stress directions. Finally, the material properties are transformed back to the x-y coordinate system thereby defining Q_{66}^k .

Fig. 5 Superposition of Variations in Buckling Stresses on Buckling Stresses to Obtain a New Principal Stress State

The first step in the derivation of Q_{66} for a single layer is to add the variations in stresses to the principal stresses in x-y coordinates as in Figure 5. The new principal stresses are, by use of the usual stress transformation,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_p &= \frac{1}{2} [(\sigma_x + \delta\sigma_x) + (\sigma_y + \delta\sigma_y)] + \sqrt{(\delta\tau_{xy})^2 + \frac{1}{4} [(\sigma_x + \delta\sigma_x) - (\sigma_y + \delta\sigma_y)]^2} \\ \sigma_q &= \frac{1}{2} [(\sigma_x + \delta\sigma_x) + (\sigma_y + \delta\sigma_y)] - \sqrt{(\delta\tau_{xy})^2 + \frac{1}{4} [(\sigma_x + \delta\sigma_x) - (\sigma_y + \delta\sigma_y)]^2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

To first order (i.e., if the variations in stresses are neglected), the new principal stresses σ_p and σ_q and σ_x and σ_y , respectively. However, we are interested in relations between compliances in the two coordinate systems so we must go beyond a first order approximation. The angle to the new principal stress state from the x-y coordinates is defined by

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{2\delta\tau_{xy}}{(\sigma_x + \delta\sigma_x) - (\sigma_y + \delta\sigma_y)} \quad (10)$$

which, for infinitesimal variations in stresses, is

$$\tan 2\alpha = \frac{2\delta\tau_{xy}}{(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)} \quad (11)$$

Moreover, for the small angle α which results,

$$\tan 2\alpha \cong \sin 2\alpha = 2\sin \alpha \cos \alpha \cong 2\sin \alpha \quad (12)$$

since $\cos 2\alpha \cong 1$ and $\cos \alpha \cong 1$. Thus,

$$\sin \alpha \cong \frac{\delta\tau_{xy}}{(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)} = k \quad (13)$$

where k is used as an abbreviation for $\sin \alpha$.

Strains in x-y coordinates can be expressed in terms of strains in new principal stress directions by application of the usual transformations [18] as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x + \delta\epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y + \delta\epsilon_y \\ \delta\gamma_{xy}/2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & k^2 & -2k \\ k^2 & 1 & 2k \\ k & -k & 1-k^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_p \\ \epsilon'_q \\ \gamma_{pq}/2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

However, the strains in new principal stress coordinates are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_p \\ \epsilon_q \\ \gamma_{pq} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11tcp}^{pq} & S_{12}^{pq} \\ S_{12}^{pq} & S_{22tcq}^{pq} \\ S_{16tcp}^{pq} & S_{26tcq}^{pq} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_p \\ \sigma_q \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where the t or c subscript is used depending on the sign of σ_p for S_{11}^{pq} and S_{16}^{pq} (hence the p subscript) and on the sign of σ_q for S_{22}^{pq} and S_{26}^{pq} (with a q subscript) in the manner of Eq. (3). The S_{ijtc}^{pq} are obtained by transformation of the tension and compression properties from the x-y coordinates (principal material directions) to the new principal stress coordinates by small angle α :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} S_{11tcp}^{pq} &= S_{11tcp}^{pq} & S_{12}^{pq} &= S_{12} & S_{16tcp}^{pq} &= -(2S_{11tcp}^{pq} - 2S_{12} - S_{66tcp}^{pq})k \\ S_{22tcq}^{pq} &= S_{22tcq}^{pq} & S_{26tcq}^{pq} &= (2S_{22tcq}^{pq} - 2S_{12} - S_{66tcq}^{pq})k \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

where terms in k^3 are neglected since they are very small compared to terms in k ($k \ll 1$ so $k^3 \ll k$). The new principal stresses are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_p \\ \sigma_q \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & k^2 & 2k \\ k^2 & 1 & -2k \\ -k & k & 1-k^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x + \delta\sigma_x \\ \sigma_y + \delta\sigma_y \\ \delta\tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Upon substitution of the new principal stresses, Eq. (17), in the strain-stress relations, Eq. (15), and the result in the strain transformation, Eq. (14), the strain-stress relations can be written as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \epsilon_x + \delta\epsilon_x &= S_{11tcp}^{pq}\sigma_x + S_{12}^{pq}\sigma_y + S_{11tcp}^{pq}\delta\sigma_x + S_{12}^{pq}\delta\sigma_y + 0(k^2) \\ \epsilon_y + \delta\epsilon_y &= S_{12}^{pq}\sigma_x + S_{22tcq}^{pq}\sigma_y + S_{12}^{pq}\delta\sigma_x + S_{22tcq}^{pq}\delta\sigma_y + 0(k^2) \\ \delta\gamma_{xy} &= (S_{66tcp}^{pq}\sigma_p - S_{66tcq}^{pq}\sigma_q) k/2 + 0(k^3) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

where $0(k^2)$ is an abbreviation for terms of order k^2 and higher. Next, subtract the prebuckling strain-stress relations, Eq. (1),

from Eq. (18) and neglect higher order terms to get the variational strain - variational stress relations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \delta \epsilon_x &= S_{11tc} \delta \sigma_x + S_{12} \delta \sigma_y \\ \delta \epsilon_y &= S_{12} \delta \sigma_x + S_{22tc} \delta \sigma_y \\ \delta \gamma_{xy} &= (S_{66tc} \sigma_p - S_{66tc} \sigma_q) k/2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (19)$$

Now substitute for k from Eq. (13) and recognize that σ_p and σ_q are essentially σ_x and σ_y , respectively, to obtain

$$\delta \gamma_{xy} = \left(S_{66tcx} \frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_x - \sigma_y} - S_{66tcy} \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_x - \sigma_y} \right) \delta \tau_{xy} \quad (20)$$

where the x or y subscript on S_{66tc} is used to denote that S_{66tc} is chosen as S_{66t} or S_{66c} on the basis of the sign of σ_x or σ_y , respectively. Finally, we identify Q_{66}^k in Eq. (8) as

$$Q_{66}^k = 1 / \left(S_{66tcx}^k \frac{\sigma_x^k}{\sigma_x^k - \sigma_y^k} - S_{66tcy}^k \frac{\sigma_y^k}{\sigma_x^k - \sigma_y^k} \right) \quad (21)$$

where

$$S_{66tcx} = \begin{cases} S_{66t} & \text{if } \sigma_x > 0 \\ S_{66c} & \text{if } \sigma_x < 0 \end{cases} \quad S_{66tcy} = \begin{cases} S_{66t} & \text{if } \sigma_y > 0 \\ S_{66c} & \text{if } \sigma_y < 0 \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

The shear compliance S_{66} is the inverse of the shear modulus. However, the tensile and compressive shear moduli, G_{xyt} and G_{xyc} , of an orthotropic material with different moduli in tension and compression cannot be measured in the usual pure shear tests. A pure shear state is inherently a state of mixed tension and compression in principal stress coordinates. Hence, the tensile and compressive shear moduli must be inferred from other data. For example, a tensile test at 45° to the principal material directions can be used to define the tensile shear modulus from the compliance transformation relation:

$$S_{66t} = \frac{1}{G_{xyt}} = \frac{4}{E_t^1} - \frac{1}{E_{xt}} + \frac{1}{E_{yt}} - \frac{2\nu_{xyt}}{E_{xt}} \quad (23)$$

where E_t^1 is the tensile modulus at 45° to the principal material directions suggested by Tsai [20]. The modulus E_c^1 is used to define S_{66c} by a relation similar to Eq. (23). Note that E_t^1 and E_c^1 and hence S_{66t} and S_{66c} are related by compliance restrictions similar

to Eqs. (4) as

$$S_{11t} - S_{11c} = S_{22t} - S_{22c} = S_{66t} - S_{66c} \quad (24)$$

The variation in stress - variation in strain relations in Eq. (8) supplemented by Eq. (21) for definition of the stiffnesses are different from Jones' weighted compliance relations [14]. Those differences all stem from the imposition of restrictions between the compliances of the present model. Specifically, here the S_{12} for each layer must be the same irrespective of whether the layer is in all-tension, all-compression, or mixed tension and compression. Moreover, of the four compliances S_{11t} , S_{11c} , S_{22t} , and S_{22c} , only three are independent because of Eq. (4). Whether these differences in stress-strain behavior models are meaningful is difficult to resolve on any theoretical grounds. That is, a material has properties for which the compliance restrictions either are or are not satisfied.

The present variation in stress - variation in strain relations are similar to those for isotropic multimodulus materials due to Jones [12] as well as to those for orthotropic multimodulus materials due to Jones [14]. Identical equations are obtained for Q_{66} in each layer when respective orthotropic results are compared and when respective isotropic results are compared. Accordingly, the only differences between Jones' weighted compliance model [14] and the present restricted compliance model are the value of S_{12} and the possibly different values of S_{11t} , S_{11c} , S_{22t} , and S_{22c} (since all four are independent in Jones' weighted compliance model [14]). Thus, comparison of the two approaches boils down to whether multimodulus materials have properties for which the compliance restrictions are satisfied.

The remainder of the buckling criterion derivation is described in the introduction to this section and is identical to that presented by Jones [14] so will not be repeated here. Of course, the stiffnesses are different from Jones' and are the major point of the foregoing derivation. The complete derivation is displayed by Jones and Morgan [21].

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Two classes of shells are appropriate for illustration of the buckling criterion developed in the previous section: (1) single-layered shells and (2) laminated shells. For single-layered shells, different moduli in tension and compression are excited only if one component of in-surface load, N_x or N_y , is tension and the other compression. Various combinations of N_x and N_y are illustrated in Figure 6. Obviously, no buckling occurs when both N_x and N_y are tension.

For laminated shells, different moduli in tension and compression are excited because of deformation compatibility between layers with different material properties. Thus, both tensile and compressive stresses can be excited in the layers even when both N_x and N_y are compressive forces. Obviously, then, different moduli in tension and

Fig. 6 Biaxial Loading Conditions

compression can be an important consideration in laminate design.

We examine both single-layered and laminated shells as numerical examples. Results are obtained for both real and hypothetical materials. Real materials are used to display the effects of different moduli in tension and compression on buckling loads of practical shells. Hypothetical materials are used to illustrate the potential effects of different moduli in tension and compression. Moreover, only by varying the parameters more widely than occurs with present materials can we begin to appreciate the behavior of multimodulus shells. The present analysis should be regarded as a sensitivity study to motivate better and more appropriate material property measurement than currently exists.

3.1 SINGLE-LAYERED SHELLS

We will address both isotropic and orthotropic single-layered shells made of materials with different behavior in tension and compression. Shells made of hypothetical isotropic multimodulus materials are studied in Section 3.1.1 to gain feeling for the multimodulus buckling problem. Shells made of several common orthotropic multimodulus materials are examined in Section 3.1.2.

3.1.1 Isotropic Single-Layered Shells

Buckling results for unstiffened isotropic multimodulus circular cylindrical shells are presented by Jones [12] in a generalized Batdorf k - Z format. Those results are obtained with a proper reduction of the present orthotropic multimodulus theory to isotropic multimodulus shells. Jones' results for a specific shell [12] will be summarized to give the reader a proper introduction to the overall problem.

Consider a circular cylindrical shell of 6-inch radius, 12-inch

length, and .1-inch thickness with a compression modulus, E_c , of 10×10^6 psi, a compression Poisson's ratio, ν_c , of .2, and the following sets of tension moduli and Poisson's ratios: $E_t = 5 \times 10^6$ psi and $\nu_t = .1$; $E_t = 10 \times 10^6$ psi and $\nu_t = .2$; and $E_t = 15 \times 10^6$ psi and $\nu_t = .3$. Note that in each case the reciprocal relations, $\nu_c E_t = \nu_t E_c$ [Eq. (2)], are satisfied.

The buckling loads for the aforementioned shell are shown in Figure 7. The behavior of the shell in the axial compression - external pressure quadrant is the same irrespective of the tension modulus. There, tension is not excited due to the membrane pre-buckling state stipulation. No buckling occurs in the axial tension - internal pressure quadrant for circular cylindrical shells.

The most striking observation that can be made about Figure 7 is that for $E_t < E_c$ the buckling load drops sharply as we pass from the axial compression - external pressure quadrant to either the axial tension - external pressure quadrant or the axial compression - internal pressure quadrant. Conversely, a sharp rise occurs for $E_t > E_c$. These discontinuities arise in Figure 7 because the compliances S_{ij} in the stress-strain relations, Eq. (1), change in a discontinuous fashion upon passing

Fig. 7 Biaxial Buckling Behavior of a Circular Cylindrical Shell with Various Tensile Moduli

from a biaxial compression state to a stress state involving both tension and compression. These discontinuities in compliances occur because of the slope discontinuity in the bilinear stress-strain model shown schematically in Figure 1. Then, note in Figure 4 that, at an unstressed point (the origin), the variation in stress can have two different signs and two different moduli. Such an unstressed point occurs, for example, in the axial direction in a shell loaded by axial compression. Thus, only as the slightest amount of tension is applied does the shell "know" it has (significantly) different moduli in tension and compression. The resulting step change in the compliances causes a large change in buckling load essentially at a point. That is, with the bilinear material model, the shell is either more or less stiff and, hence, either more or less buckling resistant in one direction or another depending on the loading.

The tension modulus apparently plays an important role for buckling in the mixed tension and compression quadrants of loading, but none at all in the biaxial compression quadrant. This fact should not be particularly surprising for a biaxial configuration such as a shell. Indeed, for a uniaxial configuration such as a ring, the circumferen-

tial bending stiffness, D_{22} , provides the primary buckling resistance and, of course, involves the compression modulus. However, for buckling of long single-layered orthotropic circular cylindrical shells under external pressure, the buckling load is approximately [21]

$$p = \frac{5.51}{Lr^{3/2}} (1 - \nu_t \nu_c)^{1/4} D_{22}^{3/4} A_{11}^{1/4} \quad (25)$$

The dominant terms are D_{22} , which involves the compression modulus, and A_{11} , which involves the tension modulus if only the slightest amount of axial tension occurs.

The buckling load discontinuity seems more pronounced for near-axial compression loading than for near-lateral pressure loading. This observation can be rationalized by examination of approximate expressions for buckling of long circular cylindrical shells under lateral pressure, p , Eq. (25), and axial compression, P , [21]:

$$P = \frac{2}{r} (1 - \nu_t \nu_c)^{1/2} A_{22}^{1/2} D_{11}^{1/2} \quad (26)$$

respectively. For lateral pressure, the axial extensional stiffness, A_{11} , has much less importance in the buckling calculation than the circumferential bending stiffness, D_{22} , because A_{11} occurs in Eq. (25) to a much lower power than D_{22} . Similarly, for axial compression, the circumferential extensional stiffness, A_{22} , has about the same importance in the buckling calculation as does the axial bending stiffness D_{11} . Thus, from Eqs. (25) and (26), the modulus in the direction normal to the principal loading has a greater effect for axial compression than for lateral pressure.

The sharp drop or rise in buckling load around pure external pressure or pure axial compression would be eliminated if the bilinear material model and its inherent slope discontinuity were replaced by a continuous stress-strain curve as indicated with the dashed line in Figure 1. However, the only portion of the present results that would be affected occurs around the discontinuities. The remainder of the present results are valid and would be approached by the more accurate material model after the discontinuities were smoothed out.

Two other behavior features are observed in Figure 7. First, the presence of internal pressure does not lead to an increase in net axial compression buckling load when $E_t \leq E_c$ (the net load is the axial load less the internal pressure component in the axial direction). The reason for this characteristic is that axisymmetric buckling ($n=0$) predominates, so lateral pressure does not appear in the buckling criterion. For $E_t = 1.5 E_c$, asymmetric buckling ($n \neq 0$) occurs as internal pressure increases until, at about 300 psi, axisymmetric buckling occurs, and the curve becomes flat. The second behavior characteristic is related to the shape of the $E_t = .5 E_c$ curve in the external pressure-axial tension quadrant. There, the addition of axial tension initially has little effect, but the "slope" of the effect rapidly becomes large and then decreases to more or less parallel the other curves as more axial tension is added.

Because of the aforementioned discontinuities in pure axial compression loading and pure external pressure loading, the fact that some composite materials have lower tension moduli than compression moduli is particularly important. The buckling behavior is very sensitive to the value of the tension moduli even though a predominately compressive load may act. This sensitivity is especially acute when the possibility exists of a small axial tension acting when predominantly external pressure is the supposed design condition (or a small internal pressure acts in conjunction with an apparently predominate axial compression). A reduction in the external buckling pressure from 175 psi to 146 psi, or 17 percent, occurs for the present shell if the tension modulus is half the compression modulus. A 30-percent reduction in axial buckling load occurs for the same shell.

The actual percentage difference between tension and compression moduli is not translated directly into the same difference in calculated buckling loads. The effect of moduli differences on the buckling load is not a magnification, but instead a reduction or diminishing of the moduli percentage difference. That is, a 10% difference between tension and compression moduli does not result in a 10% change in buckling load. Instead, a much smaller change occurs. This conclusion can be demonstrated by analyzing Eqs. (25) and (26). For lateral pressure in Eq. (25), a 10% increase in A_{11} due to a 10% increase in E_t over E_c leads to a 2.4% increase in p . Similarly, a 10% decrease in A_{11} results in a 2.6% decrease in p . For axial compression in Eq. (26), a 10% increase in $A_{22}(E_t)$ results in a 4.9% increase in P , and a 10% decrease in A_{22} leads to a 5.1% decrease in P . That is, for lateral pressure, the effect on the buckling load is essentially the factor $(1 + \%)^{1/4}$ (the symbol % is used to represent the percentage difference between tension and compression moduli) whereas the effect is $(1 + \%)^{1/2}$ for axial compression. This diminishing of the importance of moduli differences is important in buckling analysis because we then know very small moduli differences are relatively unimportant.

Some of the possible approximate methods of treating shells with different moduli in tension and compression are illustrated with the use of Figure 7. The particular case of shells with tension moduli that are half the compression moduli is discussed first. The exact solution is the line labeled $E_t = .5 E_c$; its intersections with the axial compression axis and the external pressure axis will be compared with approximate results. Three possible modulus approximations for a single modulus theory are:

1. lowest modulus (denoted by a dot at 1.8×10^5 pounds on the axial compression axis and at 85 psi on the external pressure axis);
2. compression modulus (denoted by a square at 3.7×10^5 pounds and 175 psi, respectively); and
3. average modulus (denoted by a triangle at 2.7×10^5 pounds and 130 psi, respectively).

Obviously, use of the lowest modulus (in this case the tension modulus) leads to a grossly conservative buckling prediction (too low by 30 percent for axial compression and by 42 percent for external pressure). Use of the compression modulus alone leads to unconservative results, i.e., the buckling predictions are too high by 43 percent for axial

compression and by 20 percent for external pressure. Use of the average modulus yields results that are unconservative by only 4 percent for axial compression, but for external pressure the average modulus results are conservative by 11 percent. Similar results could be shown for $E_t = 1.5 E_c$ in Figure 7. Thus, the merit of using the present approach to treating shells with different moduli in tension and compression is established.

3.1.2 Orthotropic Single-Layered Shells

Many composite materials are orthotropic and have different moduli in tension and compression. We will gain a feeling for the buckling behavior of several common composite materials for which material properties are not fully available (E_t' and E_c' are not measured).

Buckling load discontinuities Δp and ΔP are calculated by use of the BOMS III computer program (without calculating the entire interaction curve). The results for a collection of composite materials are given in percentage form in Table 2. The percentage discontinuities for long shells (Δp_{LS} and ΔP_{LS}) are calculated from Eqs. (25) and (26). However, the shells in Table 2 are not long ($L = 12"$, $r = 6"$, and $t = .06"$ except for the Avco 3-D shell where $L = 4.375"$, $r = 3"$, and $t = .08"$). Thus, the actual discontinuities are often significantly less than the long shell discontinuities. Only for the isotropic composite Sandia Felt does a buckling load discontinuity (slightly) exceed the long shell result. Accordingly, the conclusion reached in Section 3.1.1 that small differences in tension and compression moduli result in even smaller buckling load discontinuities is more generally true than just for long shells.

Table 2 Buckling Load Discontinuities for Several Composite Materials (Moduli in 10^6 psi)

MATERIAL [REFERENCE]	E_{xt}	E_{xc}	$\frac{E_{xt}-E_{xc}}{E_{xc}}$	Δp (Δp_{LS})	E_{yt}	E_{yc}	$\frac{E_{yt}-E_{yc}}{E_{yc}}$	ΔP (ΔP_{LS})
AVCO 3-D [22]	5.57	7.42	-24.9%	- 3.4% (- 6.9%)	5.74	7.73	-25.7%	- 8.7% (-13.8%)
BORON/EPOXY [3]	30	34	-11.8%	- 1.4% (- 3.1%)	3.26	3.3	- 1.2%	- .4% (- .6%)
ATJ-S GRAPHITE [6]	1.37	1.15	+19.1%	+ 4.0% (+ 4.5%)	1.93	1.52	+27.0%	+ 7.4% (+12.7%)
SANDIA C/C [23]	1.87	2.42	-22.7%	- 4.5% (- 6.2%)	.84	.94	-10.2%	- 3.2% (- 5.6%)
SANDIA FELT [23]	4.7	3.3	+42.4%	+11.0% (+ 9.2%)	4.7	3.3	+42.4%	+11.5% (+19.3%)

3.2 LAMINATED SHELLS

Laminated composite shells are used more every year. Thus, each of their behavior characteristics must be thoroughly understood. We examine the influence of different moduli in tension and compression on a two-layered shell example in Section 3.2.1 to gain appreciation for the kind of biaxial buckling behavior that can result. Moreover, we contrast the new buckling theory derived in Section 2 with that derived by Jones [14]. Then, we consider a two-layered boron/epoxy shell in Section 3.2.2 as a measure of the importance of different moduli in tension and compression in practical laminated shells.

3.2.1 Two-Layered Shell Example

Consider a two-layered shell for which the length is 12 inches, the radius is 6 inches, and each layer is .040 inch thick. Jones [24] obtained results for buckling under combinations of axial and lateral load shown in Figure 8. He used his weighted compliance material model with the following layer properties:

$$\left. \begin{array}{llll} E_{xt}^1 = 1 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yt}^1 = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyt}^1 = .3 & E_t^1 = 1.25 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ E_{xc}^1 = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yc}^1 = 4 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyc}^1 = .2 & E_c^1 = 2.5 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ E_{xt}^2 = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yt}^2 = 4 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyt}^2 = .2 & E_t^2 = 2.5 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ E_{xc}^2 = 1 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yc}^2 = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyc}^2 = .3 & E_c^2 = 1.25 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \end{array} \right\} \quad (27)$$

Each layer is an orthotropic lamina with principal material directions in the shell coordinate directions, i.e., a so-called specially orthotropic laminate. However, coupling between bending and extension exists because the layers are not symmetric about the middle surface. Note that the second (outer) layer has the same tension properties as the compression properties of the first (inner) layer. Similarly, the compression properties of the second layer are the same as the tension properties of the first layer. These material properties have the general characteristics of some current composite materials, but are not those of a specific material. Instead, the example is contrived to illustrate the changeable location of buckling load discontinuities.

Fig. 8 Buckling of a Two-Layered Shell - Weighted Compliance Model

The percentage differences between properties in tension and compression are somewhat exaggerated from all composites except carbon-carbon. Moreover, the present orthotropy ratio (1/2 or 2, depending on how you define it) is larger than that of some carbon-carbon composites in the surface of a shell configuration perpendicular to the shell surface, the stiffness is often several times higher than in the surface). On the other hand, the orthotropy ratio of this example is much less than for boron/epoxy (10) or graphite/epoxy (40).

The buckling load discontinuities for the two-layered shell in Figure 8 are much more complicated than for the single-layered shell in Figure 7. Here, both the axial and circumferential stresses in each layer can change signs. Hence, four discontinuities exist instead of the two for a single-layered shell. Moreover, the discontinuities do not occur on the axial load axis and the lateral pressure axis. Instead, the discontinuities can occur anywhere.

The curvature of the buckling load interaction curve in Figure 8 below the change in σ_x of the second layer is a consequence of the weighted compliance model. The tension and compression cross-compliance (S_{12}) are averaged as a function of the changing proportion of loads as the axial tension increases. Hence, the compliances used in the buckling calculation are changing continuously below the discontinuity and lead to the curvature noted.

The preceding two-layered shell cannot be studied with the present restricted compliance material model since the compliance restrictions, Eqs. (5) and (24), are not met by the example material properties. We arbitrarily use the compression properties of the new layer 1. Then, the tension properties of new layer 2 are the compression properties of new layer 1. The summary of layer properties is:

$$\left. \begin{array}{llll} E_{xt}^1 = 1 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yt}^1 = 1.33 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyt}^1 = .1 & E_t' = 1.11 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ E_{xc}^1 = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yc}^1 = 4 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyc}^1 = .2 & E_c' = 2.5 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ E_{xt}^2 = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yt}^2 = 4 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyt}^2 = .2 & E_t' = 2.5 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ E_{xc}^2 = 1 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yc}^2 = 1.33 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyc}^2 = .1 & E_c' = 1.11 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \end{array} \right\} (28)$$

Thus, the compliance restrictions are met for both layers.

The buckling loads for a two-layered shell with layer properties that satisfy the compliance restrictions are plotted in Figure 9. There, the buckling load discontinuities occur at quite different locations from the example in Figure 8 where the compliance restrictions are not satisfied. In fact, the load discontinuities for stress sign change in σ_x^1 and σ_x^2 between Figures 8 and 9 are interchanged in position relative to the lateral pressure axis. Moreover, the discontinuities associated with σ_y^1 and σ_y^2 are interchanged relative to the axial force axis. These differences exist because of the different orthotropy and Poisson effects of the two materials. Also, no pronounced curvature of the buckling interaction curve exists in Figure 9 near any buckling load discontinuity (because no cross-compliance weighting is used in the restricted compliance model).

The weighted compliance model and the restricted compliance model

Fig. 9 Buckling of a Two-Layered Shell - Restricted Compliance Model Fig. 10 Buckling of a Two-Layered Shell - Weighted Compliance Model (Variable S_{12} only)

are difficult to compare because of the nature of their difference. Basically, if a material satisfies the compliance restrictions, then both models lead to the same buckling load. However, we have been comparing buckling loads for two different materials [Eqs. (27) and (28)] to try to determine the influence of the model differences. The comparison of results for the two materials in Eqs. (27) and (28) is complicated by the fact that two major material property differences exist: (1) different orthotropy and (2) different Poisson effects. We will simplify the model comparison by introducing a new material which is not as different as Eq. (27) is from Eq. (28). The following material properties do not satisfy all the compliance restrictions in Eqs. (5) and (24) but differ only in Poisson effects [i.e., they satisfy Eq. (24), but not all of Eq. (5)] from the material in Eq. (28) which does satisfy the compliance restrictions:

$$\left. \begin{array}{llll}
 E_{xt}^1 = 1 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yt}^1 = 1.33 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyt}^1 = .3 & E_t^1 = 1.11 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 E_{xc}^1 = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yc}^2 = 4 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyc}^1 = .2 & E_c^1 = 2.5 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 E_{xt}^2 = 2 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yt}^2 = 4 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyt}^2 = .2 & E_t^2 = 2.5 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 E_{xc}^2 = 1 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yc}^2 = 1.33 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyc} = .3 & E_c^1 = 1.11 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}
 \end{array} \right\} (29)$$

By comparison of the buckling load interaction curves for the three materials in Eqs. (27), (28), and (29), we can determine the effects of the material model differences. The buckling load interaction curve for the material properties in Eq. (29) is plotted in Figure 10. Basically, the interaction curve in Figure 10 is quite similar in character to the interaction curve for the weighted compliance model in Figure 8. The buckling load discontinuities occur in the same relative locations. Thus, the different orthotropy in Eq. (29) versus Eq. (27) leads to the same shape of interaction curve but with somewhat different specific values of buckling loads at a given load ratio. Accordingly, the different treatment of the cross-compliances in the weighted compliance model from in the restricted compliance model leads to a drastically different interaction curve. The buckling load discontinuities for equal cross-compliances in Figure 9 are on opposite sides of the load axes from where they appear for weighted cross-compliances in either Figure 8 or 10. Thus, the effects of the cross-compliances are quite drastic. Many composite materials do not satisfy the compliance restrictions. Accordingly, which material model is used, the restricted compliance model or the weighted compliance model, must be further investigated both theoretically and experimentally.

3.2.2 Two-Layered Boron/Epoxy Shell

Boron/epoxy laminated plates and shells have been extensively studied the past few years. Most of the attention has been focused on the coupling between bending and extension due to antisymmetry or general asymmetry of the laminate. However, when different moduli in tension and compression are considered, the buckling behavior has not been evaluated.

We can construct a laminate that is antisymmetric in the usual sense [18]. That is, for a 90° layer above the middle surface, a corresponding 0° layer exists an equal distance below the middle surface. The prebuckling (membrane) stress state is the factor determining whether tension or compression material properties are appropriate in each layer. Thus, we can get mixed tension and compression stress fields in a laminate because of interlaminar strain compatibility. Hence, we can get apparently different layers, i.e., the 0° layer below the middle surface is not merely the "corresponding" 90° layer above the middle surface rotated by 90° unless the moduli are the same in tension and compression. We call these laminates antisymmetric in the geometric and fiber orientation sense. However, in the material property sense, the laminates are not antisymmetric. Specifically, we can easily show that $A_{11} \neq A_{22}$, $D_{11} \neq D_{22}$, $B_{11} \neq -B_{22}$, $B_{12} \neq 0$, and $B_{66} \neq 0$. Thus, we would expect the effect of coupling between bending and extension to be different from the usual antisymmetric laminate. However, the difference is quite small, and we will concentrate on showing what happens for a simple example.

Consider a two-layered "antisymmetric" boron/epoxy shell for which the length is 12 inches, the radius is 6 inches, and each layer is .030 inch thick. The material properties in each layer are

$$\begin{array}{llll}
 E_{xt}^1 = 30 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yt}^1 = 3.26 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyt}^1 = .21 & E_t^1 = 2.25 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 E_{xc}^1 = 34 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yc}^1 = 3.3 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyc}^1 = .238 & E_c^1 = 2.27 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 E_{xt}^2 = 3.26 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yt}^2 = 30 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyt}^2 = .0228 & E_t^2 = 2.25 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\
 E_{xc}^2 = 3.3 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_{yc}^2 = 34 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{xyc}^2 = .0231 & E_c^2 = 2.27 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}
 \end{array} \quad (30)$$

These properties are slightly modified from those in Reference 3 to satisfy the compliance restrictions.

The buckling loads for a wide range of axial and lateral forces are plotted in Figure 11. The buckling load discontinuities for this two-layered shell are even smaller than for the single-layered boron/epoxy shell in Table 2. Only those changes involving moduli jumps between 30 and 34 x 10⁶ psi are perceptible (the jumps involving moduli of 3.26 and 3.3 x 10⁶ psi are too small to be seen at this scale). In fact, the buckling load discontinuities in Figure 11 are of no practical importance. For shells with more layers, more than one layer would have a stress sign change at a time. Thus, small modulus differences have a diminished effect on buckling load discontinuities for multilayered shells as well as for single-layered shells.

Fig. 11 Buckling of a Two-Layered "Antisymmetric" Boron/Epoxy Shell

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

An exact buckling criterion, within the framework of classical buckling theory, is derived for laminated circular cylindrical shells with different orthotropic moduli in tension and compression, a feature common to many current composite materials. The buckling criterion is valid for arbitrary combinations of axial and circumferential loading. The combinations include axial compression and internal pressure as well as axial tension and external pressure. The material model (stress-strain relationship) involves a bilinear stress-strain curve with a discontinuity in slope (modulus) at the origin. New relations between the variations in stresses and variations in strains during buckling are derived. The new relations reduce for isotropic and orthotropic multimodulus materials to two relations used by Jones [12],

14]. However, the present relations are rationally derived from a restricted compliance matrix material model due to Isabekian and Khachatrian [15]. The new relations are used to obtain variations in forces and moments which are then substituted in Donnell-type buckling differential equations. Classical buckling theory, by which is implied a membrane prebuckled shape, is used for a set of simply supported edge boundary conditions.

The numerous geometrical and material parameters in the present investigation cannot be nondimensionalized in a meaningful fashion, i.e., general results cannot be presented. Accordingly, several numerical examples are given to illustrate application of the buckling criterion and to evaluate the effect of different moduli in tension and compression on buckling of practical shells. Single-layered isotropic and orthotropic shells and laminated orthotropic shells are examined.

Discontinuities in buckling loads occur as the axial and circumferential loading change relative to one another. The discontinuities were first noted by Jones [12] and are a consequence of the discontinuity in slope of the stress-strain curve. The buckling load discontinuities can occur at any combination of loads and can be predicted only by rational analysis of materials with different moduli in tension and compression. However, the magnitude of the buckling load discontinuities is substantially diminished from the level of the modulus discontinuities. For example, a 50% decrease in tension modulus from the compression modulus may lead to only a 30% decrease in axial compression buckling load if only a slight amount of internal pressure exists as opposed to a slight external pressure.

Moduli differences of the practical composite materials studied in this paper range from about 10% to about 40% with corresponding 1% to 11% jumps in the buckling loads for single-layered shells. For a boron/epoxy two-layered shell, the moduli differences are about 12% with a corresponding buckling load jump of about 2%. Thus, the influence of moduli differences on buckling load discontinuities is essentially the same for laminated shells as for single-layered shells. Accordingly, the effect of slight differences in tension and compression moduli on structural parameters such as buckling loads may be small.

More material properties must be measured for materials with different stiffness in tension and compression than for single-modulus materials. Obviously, moduli and Poisson's ratios must be measured under both uniaxial tension and uniaxial compression. However, the usual shear modulus for a single-modulus orthotropic material is not sufficient nor is it particularly meaningful. In fact, some measure of different shearing behavior in tension than in compression is essential (a simple shear test is a combination of both tensile and compressive loading so is not appropriate). The uniaxial tension and compression moduli measured at 45° to the principal material directions are sufficient to characterize these composite materials and must be reported.

The present results should serve as a guide to the conduct of experiments designed to study buckling of shells made of composite materials that exhibit different moduli in tension and compression.

5. NOMENCLATURE†

E_x, E_y	= Young's moduli in x and y directions, respectively
E_1	= Young's modulus at 45° to principal axes of orthotropy
E_1, E_2	= Young's moduli in fiber direction and transverse to fiber direction of a lamina
G_{12}	= shearing modulus of a lamina
L	= length of circular cylindrical shell (Fig. 2)
N_x, N_y	= applied axial and circumferential forces per unit length
p	= lateral pressure
P	= axial load
r	= radius to shell reference surface (Fig. 2)
S_{ij}	= compliances in strain-stress relations [Eq. (2)]
x, y, z	= axial, circumferential, and radial coordinates on shell reference surface (Fig. 2)
$\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \gamma_{xy}$	= in-plane axial, circumferential, and shear strains
$\delta\epsilon_x, \delta\epsilon_y, \delta\gamma_{xy}$	= variations in $\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y,$ and γ_{xy} during buckling
ν_{xy}	= Poisson's ratio for transverse strain in the y-direction due to stress in the x-direction
ν_{12}	= Poisson's ratio for transverse strain in the 2-direction due to stress in the 1-direction
$\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}$	= in-plane axial, circumferential, and shear stresses
$\delta\sigma_x, \delta\sigma_y, \delta\tau_{xy}$	= variations in $\sigma_x, \sigma_y,$ and τ_{xy} during buckling

Superscript

k = kth layer

Subscripts

c	= compression
p	= associated with σ_p if on S_{ijtc}
q	= associated with σ_q if on S_{ijtc}
t	= tension
x	= associated with σ_x if on S_{66tc}
y	= associated with σ_y if on S_{66tc}

† The prefix δ is used to denote the variation during buckling of the symbol which follows.

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